

grains panicle⁻¹ ($P < 0.05$) than plants covered by the mesh cage without *M. discolor* beetles. Grain yields, however, were similar, indicating that shading affects yield components. Our results showed that rice pollen feeding by *M. discolor* even at high population densities did not increase grain sterility or affect filled grain number, grain filling, and grain yield. Therefore, it can be con-

cluded that, although *M. discolor* has a phytophagous habit, it is not a pest of rice.

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Effects of rice hispa damage on grain yield

S.S. Haque and Z. Islam, Entomology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRR), Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh
 E-mail: islamz@bangla.net

Rice hispa [*Dicladispa armigera* (Olivier) (Chrysomelidae: Coleoptera)] is a major rice pest in Bangladesh. Adults feed on the green tissue of the leaf blade externally and grubs are leaf miners. Rice hispa (RH) prefers young rice plants, but, in their absence, it also attacks maturing plants. Some reports estimate time- and space-specific damage ranging from 14% to 62% yield losses from RH (Alam 1977, Karim 1987, Islam 1989, Chatterjee and Bera 1990, Nath and Dutta 1997). However, the relationship between damage level and grain loss is not clear. Therefore, we carried out several experiments at BRR under irrigated conditions in the 1999 aus (summer rice) and transplant aman (monsoon rice) seasons.

To simulate leaf damage in BR3 in the aus season and BRR Dhan 32 in the T. aman season at different plant growth stages, adult RH beetles were confined at different densities—0, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 beetles tiller⁻¹. In total, seven experiments were conducted in a randomized complete

block design with four replications. Rice plants were protected from other insect pests by applying granular insecticide (diazinon 5G) at recommended doses well before or after the treatment. In the aus season, experiments were conducted at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DAT) and at 20, 30, 50, and 70 DAT in the T. aman season. Unit plot size was 2 m × 2 m. Four rice hills (except border hills) were selected and marked in each plot. Tiller and leaf numbers were counted. Leaf damage was achieved by confining RH beetles on selected hills by a white nylon mesh cage. After 12–15 d of confinement, when the desired

level of leaf damage was achieved, beetles and cages were removed. Leaf damage was estimated visually (0–100%). Grain yields were estimated by harvesting four marked hills plot⁻¹. Yields were adjusted to 14% moisture content.

In the aus season, different densities of RH caused about 9–89% leaf damage at 20 DAT, 5–69% at 40 DAT, and 3–36% at 60 DAT, suggesting increased resistance against RH feeding with plant age. Rice plants recovered from the damage by producing new leaves. The effect of RH density on grain yield was not significant (see table).

Effect of different densities of rice hispa beetles on grain yield of rice (BR3) in the summer rice season, BRR farm, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1999.*

Hispa density (no. tiller ⁻¹)	Grain yield (g 4 hills ⁻¹)			
	20 DAT	40 DAT	60 DAT	Mean
0	99.5	74.5	95.5	89.8
0.2	83.6	94.8	98.5	92.3
0.5	102.9	80.6	93.5	92.3
1	90.2	95.8	90.7	92.2
2	85.3	83.5	100.6	89.8
4	80.4	95.9	107.5	94.6
Mean	90.3	87.5	97.7	91.8
P	ns	ns	ns	ns

*DAT = days after transplanting. Rice hispa was allowed to incur damage for 12–15 d.

In the T. aman season, different densities of RH also caused a gradient of leaf damage: 5–75% at 20 DAT, 5–53% at 30 DAT, 5–65% at 50 DAT, and 14–55% at 70 DAT. Plants apparently recovered from leaf damage by producing new leaves. However, four beetles hill⁻¹ significantly reduced grain yields regardless of the crop stage when the damage occurred. A significant negative correlation between leaf damage and grain yield was apparent (see figure). Plants suffered minor to moderate leaf damage of 0.2–2.0 RH tiller⁻¹, which did not result in significant yield losses (data not shown). Our results also suggest that photoperiod-sensitive rice grown in the monsoon season is more sensitive to yield loss from RH than photoperiod-insensitive rice grown in the summer.

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Relationship between leaf damage by hispa beetle and grain yield (var. BRRI Dhan 32) at 20, 30, 50, and 70 DAT in monsoon rice, BRRI, Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1999.

Diurnal distribution of the money spider *Atypena formosana* in the rice plant and its relation to tiller density

L. Sigsgaard and S. Villareal, IRRI, Los Baños, Philippines E-mail: les@kvl.dk

The diurnal vertical distribution of spiders is of interest to understand which prey types *Atypena formosana* (Araneae: Linyphiidae) may encounter over the course of 24 h. In this study, we visually assessed the diurnal distribution of

A. formosana in rice plants and the effect of tiller number on spider number.

Field samplings were done at the IRRI experiment station on clear sunny days with little wind. Initially, we sampled (by using a

sweep net) *A. formosana* at the panicle initiation stage of IR72 at 50 days after transplanting (DAT) on 23 Sep 1999. Temperatures ranged from 23.0 to 31.8 °C, with an average (±SD) of 28.5 ± 3.2 °C, and relative humidity (RH, ±SD)